

Engineering project - ESTACA

Evaluation of unsteady aerodynamic regimes and their influence on the aerodynamic performance of a Formula Student front wing

Phase 3 tracking sheet

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Acronyms

CFD : Computational Fluid Dynamics

GE : Ground Effect

Variables and Parameters

Non dimensional

C_L : Lift coefficient (–)

C_D : Drag coefficient (–)

Displacements

$z(t)$: Heave (m)

$\alpha(t)$: Pitch angle (rad)

Other

k : Turbulent Kinetic Energy

1. Simulation operating points

1.1. Case studies

Goals :

- to determine in which condition the car will be subjected to.
- For each case, how we will set up the simulation => What inputs we will use for each case
- What outputs we expect from the simulation.

1.1.1. Case study 1 : acceleration & braking

During acceleration & braking, the car is pitching up or down. To do the transient simulation, we need to know what kinematic behaviour the car will have under a longitudinal acceleration. To know this kinematic behaviour, we will make a simple 6 DOF vehicle model.

Pitching moment equation :

We projected newton's equation on the car's reference frame, which is accelerated. Indeed, we need to add the inertial term $M_{inertia}$ to satisfy newton's law of motion

$$M_{F_{z,r}} - M_{F_{z,f}} + M_{inertia} = I_{yy}\ddot{\phi}$$
$$\Rightarrow F_{z,r}b - F_{z,f}a + ma_x\Delta z = I_{yy}\ddot{\phi}$$

With

$$F_{z,r} = k_r z_R + c_r \dot{z}_R$$

And

$$F_{z,f} = k_f z_F + c_f \dot{z}_F$$

After linearisation :

$$F_{z,r} = k_r(z + b\theta) + c_r(\dot{z} + b\dot{\theta})$$

And

$$F_{z,f} = k_f(z - a\theta) + c_f(\dot{z} - a\dot{\theta})$$

So the final pitch equation is :

$$[k_r(z + b\theta) + c_r(\dot{z} + b\dot{\theta})]b - [k_f(z - a\theta) + c_f(\dot{z} - a\dot{\theta})]a + m a_x \Delta z = I_{yy} \ddot{\theta}$$

Heave equation :

$$m_s \ddot{z} = F_{z,r} + F_z$$

After some code, here is the result :

So finally, our wing should have this pitch variation. This variation is around the PC (pitch centre) point :

We know the coordinates of the Pitch Centre from the vehicle dynamics department $PC(x, y, z)$. We now need to determine the distance between PC and the wing, it can be done using CAD.

We suppose that the PC does not changes over time for simplification.

With EC05 Data :

Front Wheel rate	76.61	N/mm
Rear Wheel rate	74.02	N/mm
Front Damping	4.42	Ns/mm
Rear Damping	4.46	Ns/mm

With this data, we have the following pitch angle :

Check with hand calculation :

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi &= \varphi_{geo} + \varphi_{elastic} \\ \Rightarrow \varphi &= \arctan\left(\frac{RRH - FRH}{Wheelbase}\right) + \frac{M_\varphi}{K_\varphi}\end{aligned}$$

We will not consider the geometric part because our Matlab model does not have ride heights

$$\varphi = \frac{M_\varphi}{K_\varphi}$$

With

$$M_\varphi = m_{SM} a_x (h_{SM\ CoG} - h_{PC})$$

With a 2g longitudinal acceleration, we have :

$$\varphi = -0.51 \text{ deg}$$

This value is the same as the one we have in EC-05 data

In our MATLAB model, we have :

$$\varphi = -0.53 \text{ deg}$$

So our model is validated.

Check if the kinematic pitch center moves a lot or not :

We can see here 0.2mm pitch center height variation, which is negligible in our study. We can consider that the Pitch Center is at a constant height, so the trajectory of the wing is assumed as a perfect circle around the pitch axis.

	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)			
PC	970.8	0	139.48			
Wing position	-915	0	75			
R (mm)		1886.90204				

So at the end the wing will describe a circle with the shape defined by the 4DOF model

1.1.2. Case study 2 : porpoising

In this case study we assume that the car is at the exit of a corner, in a straight line. Due to ground effect, the following process will occur :

As the speed increases, the flow under the wing will get a lower pressure which leads to the wing going in the $-\vec{z}$ direction, until a point where no air can go through. Hence, the wing will begin to go up and so on.

- ⇒ If the angular frequency ω increases, the time between compression and expansion will be low and there can be non linear effects on drag and downforce

Figure 1-1. Porpoising case study

- We don't know at which frequency the car will receive that downforce in straight line. It depends on too much parameters.

What we can do is either :

- See the effect across the whole range of Downforce frequency
- Use the worst case possible : at resonance.

If we consider the second option, we will check if a resonance exists. To do that, we will assume the car as a suspended mass on an equivalent spring and on an equivalent damper :

$$m_s \ddot{z}(t) + kz(t) + c\dot{z}(t) = F_{z,aero}(t)$$

With

$$F_{z,aero}(t) = F_{z,FW+UT}(t) + F_{z,rest}$$

We will assume that only the FW and the UT are sensitive to ride height, the rest is not time dependent. We can model the aero vertical load from the FW and UT as a sinusoid, as discussed before. For the time dependent component, it has 0 downforce at 0 ride height (we assume that the RR of the wing and of the UT are the same)

To know the value A , we need to have a look in EC-05 AeroMap. With the data available, we have a maximum Force $F_{z,FW+UT}$ at 30mm of ride height : at 20 m/s

35 mm	Front Wing	Front Wheels	Body + UT	Rear Wheels	Rear Wing	Total
Downforce	228	-7	394	-22	334	927
Drag	30	16	124	28	166	364

30 mm	Front Wing	Front Wheels	Body + UT	Rear Wheels	Rear Wing	Total
Downforce	234	-7	405	-22	330	940
Drag	30	17	127	28	162	364

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{z,FW+UT,max} &= F_{z,FW,max} + F_{z,UT,max} \\
 &= 234N + 405N = 639N \\
 &\Rightarrow 2A = 639N \\
 &\Rightarrow A = 319.5N
 \end{aligned}$$

If we had the other parts contribution to downforce, we have the following expression :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Rightarrow F_{z,aero}(t) &= A\sin(\omega t) + A + F_{z,rest} \\
 \Rightarrow F_{z,aero}(t) &= A\sin(\omega t) + C
 \end{aligned}$$

With

$$F_{z,rest} = F_{z,RW} + F_{z,Wheels} = 334 - 7 - 22 = 301N$$

We will now use the model in the Laplace domain :

$$\frac{Z(s)}{F_{z,aero}(s)} = \frac{1}{m_s s^2 + cs + k}$$

Here is the bode diagram of this transfer function :

We can see that there is no resonance here, which is normal because the damping coefficient is around 0.7 in EC-05 data. Finally, the worst possible case (the highest amplitude) should be before 5 rad/s. Whatever is the value of ω from 0 to 5 rad/s, the amplitude will remain the same, with a bit of a change in phase.

We will use 5 rad/s.

In this case, we have the following heave displacement :

1.1.3. Case study 3 : Flap closed / open

Goal :

- to size the opening time Δt
- See which law is the best in terms of aero performance

Fixed opening time, different opening laws

For each opening law, plot CL vs opening time vs time

See Metrics document for more examples of output data that we can compare and things to plot.

All variables should be dimensionless, but dimensionized variables are represented for understanding.